

On the correlation between telomere shortening rate and lifespan – Supplementary material

Ion Udrouiu

Dipartimento di Scienze, Università Roma Tre, Rome, Italy

E-mail: ion.udrouiu@uniroma3.it

Methods

In order to test correlations between telomere shortening rate, maximum lifespan and body mass, all data were logarithmically transformed. When a statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) correlation was found, analysis of residuals was conducted (Speakman 2005). All analyses were investigated using phylogenetic independent contrasts (Freckleton 2012) with BayesTraits software version 3.0 (<http://www.evolution.rdg.ac.uk/BayesTraitsV3/BayesTraitsV3.html>). Since all the investigated variables are not discrete, we used the “Continuous method”, which employs a Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) sampling algorithm, using a generalized least squares approach. For each analysis, we ran one million generations, sampling every 1000 generations and discarding as burn-in the first 100,000. The phylogenetic tree (Fig. S1) for this analysis was taken from Udrouiu and Sgura (2017) and Udrouiu and Sgura (2019).

Figure S1 - Phylogenetic tree of the species surveyed in the present article. Bar represent 100 Million years.

Species	Mass (g)	Maximum lifespan (y)	TSR (bp/y)	Age at Maturity (y)	Age range for TL (y)	TSR excluding sub-adults
<i>Mus musculus</i>	20.5	4	7000	0.17	1.4-2.6	7000
<i>Capra hircus</i>	61000	20.8	363	1.5	0.85-10.1	363
<i>Ichthyaetus audouinii</i>	535	<u>20.9</u> ^a	771	3	-21.9	771
<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	101250	21.8	531	2	1.44-10.5	0
<i>Gyps fulvus</i>	7436	41.4	209	4	8.06-21.4	209
<i>Tursiops truncatus</i>	200000	51.6	766	10	8.6-50.1	376
<i>Phoenicopterus ruber</i>	3066	<u>44</u> ^b	105	?	0.79-38.8	105
<i>Elephas maximus</i>	3178000	65.5	109	15	6.14-24.7	-300
<i>Homo sapiens</i>	70000	122.5	71	18	60-100	71

Table S1 – Data for Mass, Maximum lifespan and Age at maturity are from Anage. Data for TSR (Telomere shortening rate) and Age range for TL (telomere length) are from Whittermore et al. 2019. Data for TSR excluding sub-adults are calculated from Whittermore et al. 2019.

Notes: *a* was reported by Whittermore et al. 2019 as 25 in Anage, but Anage actually reports 20.9; *b* was reported as 25 in Anage, but Anage reports it as “Not yet established”. We gave the value of 44, which is the maximum lifespan for the closest reported species, *Phoenicopterus roseus*.

Figure S2 - A: correlation between Maximum lifespan and body mass; B: correlation between TSR and Maximum lifespan; C: correlation between TSR and mass; D: correlation between residual mass (from A) and residual Maximum lifespan (from B). Same colour as in Figure 1 in the main text. Data from table S1.

Species	Mass (g)	Maximum lifespan (y)	TSR (bp/y)	Reference for TSR
<i>Mus musculus</i>	20.5	4	7000	Whittermore et al. 2019
<i>Capra hircus</i>	61000	20.8	363	Whittermore et al. 2019
<i>Capra hircus</i>	61000	20.8	400	Betts et al. 2005
<i>Ichthyaetus audouinii</i>	535	20.9	771	Whittermore et al. 2019
<i>Gyps fulvus</i>	7436	41.4	209	Whittermore et al. 2019
<i>Tursiops truncatus</i>	200000	51.6	376	Whittermore et al. 2019
<i>Phoenicopterus ruber</i>	3066	44	105	Whittermore et al. 2019
<i>Homo sapiens</i>	70000	122.5	71	Whittermore et al. 2019
<i>Homo sapiens</i>	70000	122.5	26	Daniali et al. 2013
<i>Homo sapiens</i>	70000	122.5	40	Tackney et al. 2014
<i>Homo sapiens</i>	70000	122.5	52	Rufer et al. 1999
<i>Homo sapiens</i>	70000	122.5	28	Lin et al. 2015

<i>Canis lupus</i>	40000	24	480	Benetos et al. 2011
<i>Canis lupus</i>	40000	24	136	Nasir et al. 2001
<i>Canis lupus</i>	40000	24	360	Fick et al. 2012
<i>Meles meles</i>	13000	18.6	460	Beirne et al. 2014
<i>Equus caballus</i>	300000	57	90	Denham et al. 2019
<i>Papio hamadryas</i>	18000	37.5	260	Baerlocher et al. 2003
<i>Papio hamadryas</i>	18000	37.5	121	Shepherd et al. 2007
<i>Pan troglodytes</i>	44984	59.4	73	Tackney et al. 2014
<i>Macaca fascicularis</i>	6363	39	50	Lee et al. 2002
<i>Macaca mulatta</i>	8235	40	103	Shepherd et al. 2007
<i>Bos taurus</i>	750000	20	230	Miyashita et al. 2002
<i>Ovis aries</i>	80000	22.8	300	Alexander et al. 2007
<i>Felis</i>	3900	30	394	McKevitt et al. 2003

Table S2 – Data including only adult values. Data for Mass and Maximum lifespan are from Anage.

Figure S3 - A: correlation between Maximum lifespan and body mass; B: correlation between residual mass (from A) and residual Maximum lifespan (from figure 1A in the main text). Same colour as in Figure 1 in the main text. Data from table S2.

References

Alexander, B., Coppola, G., Perrault, S.D., Peura, T.T., Betts, D.H. and King, W.A. (2007) Telomere length status of somatic cell sheep clones and their offspring. *Mol Reprod Dev* 74, 1525-37.

Baerlocher GM, Mak J, Röth A, Rice KS, Lansdorp PM. Telomere shortening in leukocyte subpopulations from baboons. *J Leukoc Biol.* 2003 Feb;73(2):289-96.

Beirne C, Delahay R, Hares M, Young A. Age-related declines and disease-associated variation in immune cell telomere length in a wild mammal. *PLoS one.* 2014 Sep 30;9(9):e108964.

Benetos A, Kimura M, Labat C, Buchoff GM, Huber S, Labat L, Lu X, Aviv A. A model of canine leukocyte telomere dynamics. *Aging cell.* 2011 Dec;10(6):991-5.

Betts DH, Perrault SD, Petrik J, Lin L, Favetta LA, Keefer CL, King WA. Telomere length analysis in goat clones and their offspring. *Mol Reprod Dev.* 2005 Dec;72(4):461-70.

Daniali L, Benetos A, Susser E, Kark JD, Labat C, Kimura M, Desai KK, Granick M, Aviv A. Telomeres shorten at equivalent rates in somatic tissues of adults. *Nature communications.* 2013 Mar 19;4:1597.

Denham J, Stevenson K, Denham MM. Age-associated telomere shortening in Thoroughbred horses. *Experimental gerontology.* 2019 Aug 31;110718.

Fick LJ, Fick GH, Li Z, Cao E, Bao B, Heffelfinger D, Parker HG, Ostrander EA, Riabowol K. Telomere length correlates with life span of dog breeds. *Cell Rep.* 2012 Dec 27;2(6):1530-6.

Freckleton RP. Fast likelihood calculations for comparative analyses. *Methods Ecol Evol.* 2012;3(5):940-947.

Lee WW, Nam KH, Terao K, Yoshikawa Y. Age-related telomere length dynamics in peripheral blood mononuclear cells of healthy cynomolgus monkeys measured by Flow FISH. *Immunology.* 2002 Apr;105(4):458-65.

Lin Y, Damjanovic A, Metter EJ, Nguyen H, Truong T, Najarro K, Morris C, Longo DL, Zhan M, Ferrucci L, Hodes RJ, Weng NP. Age-associated telomere attrition of lymphocytes in vivo is co-ordinated with changes in telomerase activity, composition of lymphocyte subsets and health conditions. *Clin Sci (Lond).* 2015 Mar;128(6):367-77.

McKevitt TP, Nasir L, Wallis CV, Argyle DJ. A cohort study of telomere and telomerase biology in cats. *Am J Vet Res.* 2003 Dec;64(12):1496-9.

Miyashita N, Shiga K, Yonai M, Kaneyama K, Kobayashi S, Kojima T, Goto Y, Kishi M, Aso H, Suzuki T, Sakaguchi M. Remarkable differences in telomere lengths among cloned cattle derived from different cell types. *Biology of reproduction.* 2002 Jun 1;66(6):1649-55.

Nasir, L., Devlin, P., McKevitt, T., Rutteman, G. & Argyle, D. J. 2001 Telomere lengths and telomerase activity in dog tissues: a potential model system to study human telomere and telomerase biology. *Neoplasia* 3, 351–359.

Rufer N, Brümmendorf TH, Kolvraa S, Bischoff C, Christensen K, Wadsworth L, Schulzer M, Lansdorp PM. Telomere fluorescence measurements in granulocytes and T lymphocyte subsets point to a high turnover of hematopoietic stem cells and memory T cells in early childhood. *J Exp Med.* 1999 Jul 19;190(2):157-67.

Shepherd BE, Kiem HP, Lansdorp PM, Dunbar CE, Aubert G, LaRochelle A, Seggewiss R, Gutterop P, Abkowitz JL. Hematopoietic stem-cell behavior in nonhuman primates. *Blood*. 2007 Sep 15;110(6):1806-13.

Speakman JR. Correlations between physiology and lifespan--two widely ignored problems with comparative studies. *Aging Cell*. 2005 Aug;4(4):167-75.

Tackney J, Cawthon RM, Coxworth JE, Hawkes K. Blood cell telomere lengths and shortening rates of chimpanzee and human females. *Am J Hum Biol*. 2014 Jul-Aug;26(4):452-60.

Udroiu I, Sgura A. The phylogeny of the spleen. *The Quarterly Review of Biology*. 2017 Dec 1;92(4):411-43.

Udroiu I, Sgura A. Rates of erythropoiesis in mammals and their relationship with lifespan and hematopoietic stem cells aging. *Biogerontology*. 2019 Aug;20(4):445-456.

Whittemore K, Vera E, Martínez-Navado E, Sanpera C, Blasco MA. Telomere shortening rate predicts species life span. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. 2019 Jul 23;116(30):15122-7.